

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Tartaric Acid by Ce(IV) Sulphate

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The kinetics of the oxidation of tartaric acid by ceric sulphate has been studied. The order of the reaction is 1. The values of ΔF and $-\Delta S$ have been calculated. The effect of different salts on the rate of reaction has also been studied. H^+ ions in H_2SO_4 have been found to retard the rate of reaction.

Benrath and Ruland¹ studied the oxidation of tartaric acid by ceric sulphate. Willard and Young² oxidised the same by ceric sulphate, confirming the formation of formic acid as the oxidation product. Sharma and Mehrotra³, following Willard and Young², showed that tartaric acid could be oxidised to CO_2 stage by refluxing with ceric sulphate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid and suggested that complete oxidation of the above acid could be used as a satisfactory method for the quantitative estimation of tartaric acid. In the present communication the oxidation of tartaric acid by ceric sulphate has been studied from the stand point of kinetics.

EXPERIMENTAL

E. Merck's (G.R.) ceric ammonium sulphate solution in $2N-H_2SO_4$ was prepared and used as a stock solution.

E. Merck's (G.R.) tartaric acid solution was prepared and estimated by acid-alkali titrations. The experimental procedure followed was the same as described previously⁴. Some of the experiments were carried out by spectrophotometric method. The amount of ceric ion consumed per mole of tartaric acid was determined as the acid requiring 6 equivalents of ceric sulphate, the oxidation product being formic acid, confirmed by the chromotropic acid reaction.

Order of Reaction.—Oxidation of tartaric acid was effected in presence of ceric ions, using up to ten-fold excess (Fig. 1 & 2; Tables I & II). When ceric sulphate is in excess or in equivalent amount, the plot of $\log(a/a-x)$ or $\log [(O.D.)_0/(O.D.)_t]$ [where a , $a-x$, $(O.D.)_0$, and $(O.D.)_t$ have the usual significances] against t provides a straight line, indicating that the reaction is of the first order with respect to ceric ion.

Effect of pH on the Reaction.—The reaction was retarded by H_2SO_4 . The curve representing $\log K$ against pH due to H_2SO_4 is linear within the limits studied. The pH of the solution was adjusted with H_2SO_4 (Fig. 4)

1. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 114, 267.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 132.
3. *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 11, 417, 507.
4. Sengupta *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 823.

TABLE I
Temp. = 25°.

[Tartaric acid].	[Ceric sulphate].	pH.	$K \times 10$ (min ⁻¹).
0.02530M	0.02500M	1.14	12.510
"	"	0.80	5.066
"	"	0.64	2.703
0.01859	0.01823	0.98	2.212
0.01549	0.01524	0.74	3.224

FIG. 1

TABLE II
Temp. = 30°. pH = 1.04.
[Ceric sulphate] = 0.0244M.

[Tartaric acid].	$K \times 10$ (min ⁻¹).
0.01240M	13.82
0.00826	12.80
0.00495	5.52
0.00248	1.61

FIG. 2

Effect of Oxidants on the Reaction Rate.—Oxidations with about 2,3,5, and 10-fold excess of Ce (IV) ions were followed (Table II). The reaction slowed down as the ratio of ceric to the organic acid was increased. The consumption of ceric ion always followed the first-order rate. It is interesting to note that the reaction is directly proportional to the concentration of tartaric acid.

Influence of Salts on the Reaction Velocity.—Different salts, such as NaClO₄, KCl, KNO₃, MgSO₄, and Na₂SO₄, were used. Salt effect was not observed in NaClO₄ solution. Addition of KCl or KNO₃ produced no significant retardation. Both Na₂SO₄ and MgSO₄ retarded the rate of reaction (Table III).

TABLE III

A. [Tartaric acid] = 0.01859M. [Ceric sulphate] = 0.01823M. pH = 0.90. Temp. = 25°.		B. [Tart. acid] = 0.0071M. [Ce ^{IV} sulphate] = 0.133M. [H ₂ SO ₄] = 0.301N. Temp = 5°.		
[Salt] × 10.	$K \times 10$ (min ⁻¹).	[Salt] × 10.	$K_{Na_2SO_4} \times 10^2$ (min ⁻¹).	$(K_{MgSO_4} \times 10^2)$ (min ⁻¹).
0	8.06	Nil	9.212	9.212
2.5M-NaClO ₄	"	1.25M	4.606	5.757
2.5M-Na ₂ SO ₄	3.684	2.50	3.454	4.606
2.5M-MgSO ₄	4.836	3.75		3.460

Influence of Temperature on the Reaction Velocity.—The reaction velocities were measured at three different temperatures (Table IV). All the three experiments were performed at identical pH (Fig. 3 represents a typical plot). From the linear plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 5), the activation energy was calculated. The activation energy and the entropy of activation ($-\Delta S$) are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

A. [Tartaric acid] = 0.0168M. [Ceric sulphate]=0.0244M. pH = 0.86.

Temp.	25°	15°	5°	} $\Delta E=11.0 \pm 0.4$ kcal./mole $-\Delta S=33.7 \pm 1.0$ (e.u.)
$K \times 10(\text{min}^{-1})$	4.600	2.303	1.151	

B. [Tartaric acid] = 0.0101M. [Ceric sulphate] = 0.0244M.

[H ₂ SO ₄].	$K \times 10(\text{min}^{-1})$			$\Delta E(\text{kcal.})$	$-\Delta S(\text{e.u.})$
	23°.	17°.	11°.		
0.5254N	3.915	1.840	1.3810	13.8 ± 0.4	23.64 ± 1.5
0.7754	2.533	1.151	0.9212	17.5 ± 0.6	11.68 ± 1.0
0.9780	1.612	0.601	0.3454	21.2 ± 0.7	1.84 ± 0.3

FIG. 3

In Fig. 3 curves marked by $\odot$, $\bullet$, and $\triangle$ refer respectively to 5°, 15° and 25°.

FIG. 4

DISCUSSION

When tartaric acid is oxidised by ceric sulphate, CO₂ is evolved and formic acid remains in solution. When a large excess of ceric ion is present, a total of about 6 equivalents of ceric ion is eventually consumed per mole of tartaric acid and one mole of tartaric acid produces two equivalents of formic acid². Consequently

could represent the stoichiometry of the equation. Glyoxylic acid is the possible intermediate, this being rapidly oxidised by ceric salt⁵.

5. Smith and Duke, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 120.

Taube⁶ has suggested that during the oxidation of oxalate ion by chlorine, catalysed by Mn(III) ion, a manganese oxalato chelate is first formed. The electron pull of the trivalent manganese is so great that an electron is donated to the metal with simultaneous breaking of the C-C bond. This constitutes the first step in the reaction chain and is followed by a number of rapid steps. Similar is the case when glycol is oxidised by ceric ion⁷. On the basis of the above explanations, the oxidation of tartaric acid may be suggested as follows:

FIG. 5

with Ce(IV) ion to afford two moles of glyoxylic acid. Each mole of glyoxylic acid is then hydrated and oxidised to formic acid with the consumption of two equivalents of ceric ion; for two moles of glyoxylic acid four equivalents of ceric ions are required.

In postulating the reaction rate, Bodenstein's steady-state method is applied. The reaction steps are:

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1413; 1948, **70**, 1216,

7. Duke and Forist, *ibid.*, 1947, **69**, 2885,

where TA and A[•] are tartaric acid and the corresponding free radical; Gl and B[•] are glyoxylic acid and the corresponding free radical. For the other mole of glyoxylic acid, steps (4) and (5) will be repeated to provide another mole of formic acid.

Under steady-state condition⁹, the concentration of the radicals will be constant and if $K_2 \gg K_3$, i.e., if the process (3) is a slower one, consumption of ceric ion will be given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{IV}]}{dt} = K[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$$

This accounts for the first-order disappearance of ceric ions.

Coming to thermodynamic constants, it is seen that the activation energy does not remain constant, but increases as the concentration of H₂SO₄ is increased. This is possibly due to the fact that H₂SO₄ reacts with Ce(SO₄)₂ to afford stronger complexes.

The inhibiting effect of addition of sulphates or sulphuric acid can also be explained in the light of the complex nature of ceric sulphate in solution⁹⁻¹⁰. This has been explained in the previous communication⁴.

The low value of the activation energy of the oxidation and the absence of any effect of addition of an indifferent salt, e.g. NaClO₄, on the rate of oxidation support the above picture of free radical mechanism.

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8. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, **35**, 329.

9. Hardwick and Robertson, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1951, **29**, 818, 828.

10. Moore and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1470.